

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

PROSPECTS FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF AZERBAIJAN IN THE CONTEXT OF ACCESSION TO THE WTO: PROS AND CONS

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Abstract

This article analyzes the prospects for economic growth and integration of the Republic of Azerbaijan into the World Trade Organization (WTO). In the context of globalization and increasing international competition, accession to the WTO is an important step to expand trade opportunities and stimulate economic development of Azerbaijan. The article analyzes how integration into the global trading system can improve the business environment, ensure more stable and transparent conditions for doing business, and attract foreign direct investment. Particular attention is paid to how WTO membership can help Azerbaijan diversify its economy, reduce dependence on the oil sector and develop new industries such as information technology, agriculture and tourism. In addition, the article examines the potential challenges and risks associated with the WTO accession process. Possible negative consequences for local producers, who may face increasing competition from foreign companies are also considered. Measures to be taken to protect national interests and support domestic enterprises in the context of trade liberalization are assessed.

Keywords: World Trade Organization (WTO), economic growth, Republic of Azerbaijan, accession, legislative reforms.

Azerbaijan has the largest economy in the South Caucasus, however, the republic was the last of the three countries in the region to join the WTO. Azerbaijan is in no hurry to join the World Trade Organization, explaining its position by the fact that it should carefully consider all the pros and cons of this step. And there is a reasonable explanation for this - as has already been noted, membership in the WTO, in addition to trade advantages, also brings a lot of negative aspects to the country.

Azerbaijan's accession to the WTO can already be considered a relatively long process, which has been going on for 18 years. Azerbaijan has had observer status in the World Trade Organization (WTO) since 1997, and since 2004, negotiations have been underway to join the WTO [1]. This process includes careful adjustment of the domestic economy and legislation in accordance with international WTO standards, which requires time and effort to ensure compliance and successful integration into the global trading environment.

One of the reasons for the long period of Azerbaijan's accession to the WTO is that the country's economy is considered to be the leader among the economies of neighboring countries that have joined the organization. The issues of gain and loss from accession to the WTO for Azerbaijan can be assessed from different aspects and here not only the profitability of countries is assessed, the classification of these profits by different sectors is very important. In the current situation, the subject of discussion should not be the issue of accession to the WTO or not, but how to implement accession to the WTO so that Azerbaijan can benefit from it as much as possible.

For the successful participation of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the WTO, it is necessary to focus on the development of the most vulnerable industries, taking

into account both innovative achievements within these industries and beyond. An important step is also the adoption of regulatory and legal acts that contribute to increasing the investment attractiveness of the country. The solution of these problems will require systematic and coordinated work of all levels of government, which will allow an effective integration into the global trading system and strengthen the economic position of Azerbaijan.

Let us to remind that Azerbaijan is negotiating in four main areas:

- about goods (tariffs on agricultural and industrial products);
- in the field of trade in services;
- improvement of national legislation (in accordance with WTO requirements)
- and support for agriculture (subsidies) [2].

Despite the fact that the size of the Azerbaijani economy is incomparable with the economies of distant and nearby countries, the establishment of an integrated economic space with the CIS countries plays a fundamentally important role in the development of the economy in the long term. Such interdependence is observed in several areas.

If Azerbaijan joins the WTO, one of the first consequences of the crisis could be a sharp decrease in the competitiveness of goods from the CIS countries on the Azerbaijani market and vice versa, as well as a decrease in mutual trade turnover. In particular, in 2023, Azerbaijan's trade turnover with the CIS countries increased by 10%. Over 11 months, exports worth 1 billion 502 million 99 thousand US dollars (1.7% more than a year ago) and imports worth 4 billion 348 million 929 thousand US dollars (12.4% more) were carried out between Azerbaijan and the CIS countries (fig. 1) [3].

Figure 1. Trade turnover of Azerbaijan with the CIS countries for 11 months of 2023.

During the reporting period, the share of CIS countries in Azerbaijan's total exports amounted to 4.8%, while their share in total imports was 27.5%. During this period, Azerbaijan's largest trade turnover was carried out consistently with Russia, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Belarus, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova and Tajikistan [3].

The economy of Azerbaijan demonstrates significant growth and development despite the fact that the country is not a member of the World Trade Organization (WTO). In 2023 alone, Azerbaijan carried out trade operations with 193 countries, the top ten of which included the following countries (table 1, 2) [4]:

Table 1.

Share of main trading partners in Azerbaijan's exports in 2023.

Countries	In percentage	Place
Italy	44	1
Turkey	15.8	2
Israel	4.13	3
Greece	4.02	4
India	3.64	5
Russia	3.52	6
Germany	2.67	7
Spain	2.31	8
Georgia	2.24	9
Czech Republic	2.01	10

Table 2.

Share of main trading partners in Azerbaijan's imports in 2023.

Countries	In percentage	Place
Russia	18.2	1
Китай	17.4	2
Turkey	13.2	3
Germany	5.26	4
USA	5.14	5
Turkmenistan	3.97	6
Italy	2.76	7
Iran	2.73	8
Japan	2.51	9
South Korea	2.47	10

Experts believe that Azerbaijan's accession to the WTO is not so much necessary as inevitable. However, this should only happen on acceptable terms. Azerbaijan needs to further strengthen its economy. In this regard, it is important to carefully consider all the pros and cons that WTO membership will bring to the country.

Among the advantages of joining the WTO, the following can be highlighted:

- acceleration of the integration process into the global economic system;
- expansion of the range of goods and services for consumers;
- increase in income, since the reduction of trade barriers will contribute to the strengthening of trade activities, which will lead to an increase in both state and personal income;
- increase in the level of employment;
- increase in the efficiency of foreign economic activity (FEA);
- the opportunity to participate in WTO decision-making, including the issues related to commodity markets;
- granting Azerbaijan the most favored treatment in relations with all WTO members;
- ensuring equal conditions for all participants in international trade;
- accession to the WTO not only contributes to the free movement of goods, but also capital, in particular foreign direct investment, which plays an important role in the development of the national economy;
- expansion of opportunities to influence the adoption of fundamental decisions in the field of trade within the framework of WTO legislation;
- the principle of reducing customs duties, which contributes to an increase in foreign trade turnover;
- diversification of the national economy and increasing the export potential of the country's non-oil sector.

Accession to the WTO can bring significant economic benefits, but only on condition that clear priorities are established in the socio-economic development of the country. Considering the various economic and political problems on the way to accession to the WTO, one can agree with the opinion of domestic scientists and experts: why should Azerbaijan join an organization that imposes such unfavorable conditions on it?

Nevertheless, according to experts, Azerbaijan's accession to the WTO may require the abandonment of some principles, which may lead to certain negative consequences for various sectors of the economy. In particular:

- due to the reduction of import tariffs and the facilitation of the promotion of foreign goods and services to the Azerbaijani market, the protection of domestic producers will become more difficult;
- due to the reduction of import customs duties, the receipt of funds to the state budget will decrease;
- difficulties may arise in the process of economic integration with the CIS countries;
- membership in the WTO will limit the state's ability to regulate foreign economic activity;

- a decrease in budget revenues may reduce state investment in the infrastructure of industry development;

- Azerbaijan will be limited in its ability to make independent economic decisions;

- Azerbaijan is represented on the world market mainly by raw materials and with accession to the WTO it will be more difficult to get rid of raw material dependence;

- the lack of competitiveness of many Azerbaijani companies may lead to job losses and an increase in unemployment;

- Azerbaijan's accession to the WTO may negatively affect agriculture, since the market will be filled with cheap imported agricultural goods with which local producers will not be able to compete. As a result, agriculture may decline, which will lead to a decrease in the standard of living in rural areas and an increase in the country's dependence on imported food products;
- the financial sector may also suffer significantly.

The opening of branches of foreign financial and insurance companies will provide local citizens and companies with access to more profitable, long-term and cheap credit resources, as well as higher-quality services. This will create serious problems for the survival of Azerbaijani banks and insurance companies, which will not be able to compete on equal terms.

Speaking at a conference on the economic development of the country's regions, the President of Azerbaijan said: "An analysis of the possible positive and negative consequences of the country's accession to the WTO showed that Azerbaijan does not intend to join the World Trade Organization (WTO) in the near future... Each country must protect its market and Azerbaijan is following this path. Azerbaijan will join the WTO when agriculture and industry are export-oriented" [5].

In order to protect local producers, Azerbaijan is seeking to join the WTO with the status of a developing country. While the WTO insists on assigning Azerbaijan the status of a developed country, arguing that all CIS countries have joined the organization with this status. If Azerbaijan becomes a member of the WTO as a developing country, this will allow the republic to provide more significant financial support to the agricultural sector, maintaining subsidies at the level of 10% of the gross agricultural product.

In conclusion, I would like to note that on June 6, 2024, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan met General Director of the World Trade Organization (WTO) Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala. At the meeting, an exchange of views took place on the process of Azerbaijan's accession to the World Trade Organization [6].

Thus, despite all the advantages and disadvantages, joining the WTO means for Azerbaijan integration into the current system of rules for the movement of goods and services on the world market.

References

1. Azerbaijan has raised the status of the WTO accession commission. - <https://report.az/ru/biznes/azerbajdzhan-povysil-status-komissii-po-vstupleniyu-v-vto/>

2. <https://report.az/ru/biznes/azerbajdzhan-pov-ysil-status-komissii-po-vstupleniyu-v-vto/> - Azerbaijan has raised the status of the WTO accession commission, June 8, 2021

3. https://cis.minsk.by/news/26732/tovarooborot_azerbajdzhana_so_stranami_sng_uvelichilsja_v_2023_godu_na_10 - Azerbaijan's trade turnover with the CIS countries increased by 10% in 2023.

4. <https://interfax.az/view/907949> - Azerbaijan's positive balance in foreign trade in 2023 decreased by 30%.

5. Aliyev I. G. Speech at the conference dedicated to the results of the first year of implementation of the "State Program for the Socio-Economic Development of the Regions of Azerbaijan for 2014-2018".

6. <https://president.az/ru/articles/view/66206> - Ilham Aliyev meet the General Director of the World Trade Organization.